

CAREER DEVELOPMENT PLAN - YEAR 1

Deliverable 1.1

Name of fellow: Neemias Santos da Rosa

Department: UMR5199 PACEA (University of Bordeaux)

Name of Supervisor: Francesco d'Errico

Date: 14/02/2024

1. BRIEF OVERVIEW OF THE RESEARCH PROJECT AND MAJOR ACCOMPLISHMENTS EXPECTED:

The advent of symbolic material culture and the storage of information outside the human brain through the production of artefacts and images imbued with meaning was a landmark in human evolution. Although it has been generally considered as the consequence of an European Upper Palaeolithic "revolution" that took place around 40 ka, new evidence from the Middle Stone Age (MSA, ~300–40 ka) suggests the presence of symbolic material culture in Africa at ~150 ka. In this context, a major research challenge for archaeology is to explain the apparent absence of rock art paintings in the MSA located on the coast of southern Africa. Ochre pigments are ubiquitous in the sites from this period, and toolkits used to produce ochre-rich liquid paint date from at least ~100 ka. Furthermore, images engraved on pieces of ochre and a crayon drawing demonstrate that the MSA populations had all the material, technical and cognitive resources necessary to create graphic representations. However, the oldest rock art paintings in the area are much more recent and date back to the Later Stone Age. One of the possible explanations for this scenario would be that rock art paintings never existed in the MSA, and that it reflects a cultural choice of human groups who decided not to paint images on the walls of caves and shelters. Nevertheless, building such an inference based only on the fact that we have not yet found these painted images, is problematic from the point of view of scientific reasoning, given that, epistemologically, the absence of evidence is not evidence of absence. On the other hand, since rock art paintings tend to be affected by a series of mechanical, physicochemical, and biological processes that influence their preservation, the alternative explanation is of taphonomic nature. In this sense, many scholars have emphasized that the prehistoric artistic record we observe in the present, is not

an accurate reflection of the past, but the result of a taphonomic bias, introduced by time-dependent destructive processes, that affect especially the painted images.

Thus, through an innovative and interdisciplinary approach that brings together an international team of experts in archaeology, paleoenvironmental science, atmospheric science, material science, and analytical chemistry (from the University of Bordeaux, the University of the Basque Country, the German Aerospace Center, and the University of Bergen), the TaphArt project aims to develop an experimental research to systematically investigate whether the absence of rock art paintings in coastal MSA sites of southern Africa is more likely the product of cultural choices or the result of taphonomic processes that eliminated the painted images from the archaeological record. Taking as reference the archaeological and paleoenvironmental context of Blombos Cave (South Africa), we will develop a series of accelerated ageing experiments to investigate whether marine aerosol degradation and wind erosion may have contributed to the destruction of rock art paintings potentially produced on the site. Building on the findings of this study, we will build a predictive model to determine how long and under which environmental conditions rock art paintings can survive these taphonomic phenomena, providing groundbreaking unprecedented data to the discussion on the origins of rock art and the behavioural evolution of the *Homo sapiens*.

2. LONG-TERM CAREER OBJECTIVES (over 5 years):

1. Goals:

- Secure funding through an ERC Starting or Consolidator Grant to continue and expand (geographically and chronologically) my research on rock art taphonomy and technology.
- Obtain a Ramon y Cajal Postdoctoral Fellowship at a Spanish university and, by the end of the 5-year contract, secure a tenure-track position within the institution.
- To become an international reference in the study of prehistoric technology and rock art taphonomy through experimental archaeology.

2. What further research activity or other training is needed to attain these goals?

- To attend training sessions on how to apply for ERC Funding.
- To prepare, with the guidance of the current supervisor, a project to apply for an ERC Starting Grant in the 2025 call.

- To broaden my portfolio of publications as the first author in prestigious journals like Scientific Reports, Quaternary Science Reviews, Journal of Human Evolution, and Science Advances.
- To increase my teaching experience, especially at institutions outside Spain.
- To achieve higher proficiency and autonomy in performing microscopic analyses of archaeological materials and chemical analyses of rock art pigments.
- To pursue in-depth training in applied statistics artificial intelligence techniques.
- To expand my research network and collaborate on projects developed in other European countries and other continents.

3. SHORT-TERM OBJECTIVES (1-2 years):

3.1 Research results

▪ **Anticipated publications**

Journal articles (Peer-reviewed):

- Fiore, D., Butto, A., Acevedo, A., **Santos da Rosa, N.** “El arte del chiejaus: análisis de artefactos pintados para la ceremonia mixta de iniciación Yagan (1920-1922, Tierra del Fuego, Extremo Sur de Sudamérica)”. Boletín del Museo Chileno de Arte Precolombino. *Under review (submitted on December 22, 2023)*.
- **Santos da Rosa, N.**, Fiore, D. & Viñas, R. “Hairs, plants, or feathers? An experimental approach to the paint application tools used in the production of Levantine rock art (eastern Spain)”. Journal of Archaeological Science: Reports. *In preparation (to be submitted on February 2024)*.
- González-Vázquez, N., García-Atiénzar, G., **Santos da Rosa, N.**, Villalobos, C., de la Luz Gutiérrez, M. & Díaz-Andreu, M. “Using GIS to explore prehistoric senses: a new approach to Gran Mural rock art (Baja California Sur, Mexico)”. Latin American Antiquity. *In preparation (to be submitted on March 2024)*.
- **Santos da Rosa, N.** “How to conduct archaeological experiments”. Advances in Archaeological Practices – How-to Series. *In preparation (to be submitted on May 2024)*.
- Laue, G. & **Santos da Rosa, N.** “Connecting image-makers: technological networks and communities of practice in San rock art (South Africa)”. Cambridge Archaeological Journal. *In preparation (to be submitted on June 2024)*.
- **Santos da Rosa, N.**, d’Errico, F., Maguregui, M., Fiore, D., et al. “The role of environmental factors on the taphonomy of rock art paintings: a

comprehensive review”. *Journal of Cultural Heritage. In preparation (to be submitted on July 2024).*

- **Santos da Rosa, N.** & Fiore, D. “Rock art’s materiality, technological performances and techno-visual affordances: a theoretical-methodological framework developed in Patagonia and its application in the Spanish Levante”. *World Archaeology – Special Issue Revolutionising Rock Art*, edited by Valdez-Tullet, J., Figueiredo, S. & Ouzman, S. *In preparation (to be submitted on August 2024).*
- Díaz-Andreu, M., **Santos da Rosa, N.**, Alvarez-Morales, L. “An archaeology of the invisible? Exploring the acoustics of rock art landscapes through a multidisciplinary approach. *World Archaeology – Special Issue Revolutionising Rock Art*, edited by Valdez-Tullet, J., Figueiredo, S. & Ouzman, S. *In preparation (to be submitted on August 2024).*
- **Santos da Rosa, N.**, d’Errico, F., Maguregui, M., Wiesinger, F., et al. “The breeze of decay: an experimental approach to the impact of marine aerosol degradation in coastal rock art sites”. *Plos One. To be prepared (expected date of submission: November 2024).*
- **Santos da Rosa, N.**, d’Errico, F., Maguregui, M., Wiesinger, F., et al. “Blowing in the wind: using accelerated ageing experiments to model the impact of aeolian erosion on coastal rock art paintings”. *Scientific Reports. To be prepared (expected date of submission: March 2025).*
- **Santos da Rosa, N.**, d’Errico, F., Maguregui, M., Wiesinger, F., et al. “Developing a predictive model to estimate the preservation rate of rock art paintings against the impact of marine aerosol degradation and wind erosion: a case study from the Southern Cape coast of South Africa”. *Quaternary Science Review. To be prepared (expected date of submission: June 2025).*
- **Santos da Rosa, N.**, d’Errico, F., Maguregui, M., Wiesinger, F., et al. “The absence of rock art paintings in coastal Middle Stone Age sites of Southern Africa: is it the result of cultural choices or taphonomic processes?”. *Journal of Human Evolution. To be prepared (expected date of submission: November 2025).*
- **Santos da Rosa, N.**, d’Errico, F., Maguregui, M., Wiesinger, F., et al. “The impact of climate change on coastal rock art sites: a predictive model based on accelerated ageing experiments”. *Science Advances. To be prepared (expected date of submission: March 2026).*

Book chapters (Peer-reviewed):

- Díaz-Andreu, Margarita, Laura Fernández Macías, and **Neemias Santos da Rosa**. “From Graceful and Feminine to Silenced: The Study of Female Representations in Levantine Rock Art.” In *Où Sont Les Femmes? L’archéologie Du Genre Dans La Préhistoire et La Protohistoire*, edited by

Anne Augereau and Caroline Trémeud. Nanterre: Société Préhistorique Française. *In press (expected date of publication: March 2024)*

- Díaz-Andreu, Margarita, Lidia Alvarez-Morales, and **Neemias Santos da Rosa**. “The archaeoacoustics of rock art sites: a methodological review. In “New sensory approaches to the past: applied methods in sensory heritage and archaeology”, edited by Pamela Jordan, Sara Mura, and Sue Hamilton. London: UCL Press. *In press (expected date of publication: September 2024)*
- **Santos da Rosa, N.**, Benítez-Aragón, D., Alvarez-Morales, L. “The sonorous dimension of San rock art: an archaeoacoustic approach to Game Pass Shelter”. In Game Pass Shelter, edited by Hollman, J., Laue, G. & Wintjes, J. Johannesburg: Wits University Press. *In press (expected date of publication: November 2024)*.
- Díaz-Andreu, M., Pasalodos, R., **Santos da Rosa, N.**, Benítez-Aragón, D., Alvarez-Morales, L. “Shamans’ soundscapes: the archaeoacoustics of Karakol rock art (Republic of Altai, Russia). In Exploring ancient sounds and places: theoretical and methodological approaches to archaeoacoustics, edited by Díaz-Andreu, M. & Santos da Rosa, N. Oxford: Oxbow. *In press (expected date of publication: November 2024)*.

Book:

- Díaz-Andreu, M. & **Santos da Rosa, N.** Exploring ancient sounds and places: theoretical and methodological approaches to archaeoacoustics. Oxford: Oxbow. *In press (expected date of publication: November 2024)*.
- **Anticipated conference, workshop attendance, courses, and /or seminar presentations:**

Conferences:

- **Santos da Rosa, N.**, d’Errico, F., Maguregui, M., Wiesinger, F., Fiore, D., Queffelec, A., Courtenay, L., Caruso, F., van Niekerk, K., Henshilwood, C. “TaphArt: an experimental approach to the impact of wind erosion and marine aerosol degradation on coastal rock art sites”. *30th Annual Meeting of the European Association of Archaeologists*. Rome – Italy (28-31 August 2024).
- Santos da Rosa, N. “On the taphonomy of rock art: using accelerated ageing experiments to model the impact of marine aerosol degradation and wind erosion on prehistoric paintings”. *8th International Congress “The Art of Prehistoric Societies”*. Salamanca – Spain (6-10 November 2024).

- **Santos da Rosa, N., d’Errico, F., Maguregui, M., Wiesinger, F., Fiore, D., Queffelec, A., Courtenay, L., Caruso, F., van Niekerk, K., Henshilwood, C.** “Title to be determined” [Presentation of the results of the MSCA TaphArt Project]. *10th World Archaeological Congress*. Adelaide – Australia (6-10 November 2024).
- **Santos da Rosa, N., d’Errico, F., Maguregui, M., Wiesinger, F., Fiore, D., Queffelec, A., Courtenay, L., Caruso, F., van Niekerk, K., Henshilwood, C.** “Title to be determined” [Presentation of the results of the MSCA TaphArt Project]. *31th Annual Meeting of the European Association of Archaeologists*. Belgrade – Serbia (3-6 September 2025).

Workshops:

- **Santos da Rosa, N., d’Errico, F., Maguregui, M., Wiesinger, F., Fiore, D., Queffelec, A., Courtenay, L., Caruso, F., van Niekerk, K., Henshilwood, C.** “Title to be determined” [Presentation of the MSCA TaphArt Project]. *Beyond images: rethinking the presence, absence and meaning of prehistoric and Indigenous rock depictions*. Tel Aviv – Israel (September 2024).
- **Santos da Rosa, N., d’Errico, F., Maguregui, M., Wiesinger, F., Fiore, D., Queffelec, A., Courtenay, L., Caruso, F., van Niekerk, K., Henshilwood, C.** “Title to be determined” [Presentation of the results of the MSCA TaphArt Project]. *TaphArt Project Workshop*. Bordeaux – Israel (August 2025).

Seminars:

- **Santos da Rosa, N., d’Errico, F., Maguregui, M., Wiesinger, F., Fiore, D., Queffelec, A., Courtenay, L., Caruso, F., van Niekerk, K., Henshilwood, C.** “Title to be determined” [Presentation of the MSCA TaphArt Project]. *31th Department of Analytical Chemistry of the University of the Basque Country*. Bilbao – Spain (April 2024).
- **Santos da Rosa, N., d’Errico, F., Maguregui, M., Wiesinger, F., Fiore, D., Queffelec, A., Courtenay, L., Caruso, F., van Niekerk, K., Henshilwood, C.** “Title to be determined” [Presentation of the MSCA TaphArt Project]. *Institute of Solar Research of the German Aerospace Center*. Almería – Spain (June 2024).
- **Santos da Rosa, N., d’Errico, F., Maguregui, M., Wiesinger, F., Fiore, D., Queffelec, A., Courtenay, L., Caruso, F., van Niekerk, K., Henshilwood, C.** “Title to be determined” [Presentation of the MSCA TaphArt Project]. *Institute of Solar Research of the German Aerospace Center*. Almería – Spain (June 2024).

- **Santos da Rosa, N., d’Errico, F., Maguregui, M., Wiesinger, F., Fiore, D., Queffelec, A., Courtenay, L., Caruso, F., van Niekerk, K., Henshilwood, C.** “Title to be determined” [Presentation of the MSCA TaphArt Project]. *Center for Early Sapiens Behaviour of the University of Bergen*. Bergen – Norway (September 2024).
- **Santos da Rosa, N., d’Errico, F., Maguregui, M., Wiesinger, F., Fiore, D., Queffelec, A., Courtenay, L., Caruso, F., van Niekerk, K., Henshilwood, C.** “Title to be determined” [Presentation of the MSCA TaphArt Project]. *Institute of Solar Research of the German Aerospace Center*. Almería – Spain (June 2024).
- **Santos da Rosa, N., d’Errico, F., Maguregui, M., Wiesinger, F., Fiore, D., Queffelec, A., Courtenay, L., Caruso, F., van Niekerk, K., Henshilwood, C.** “Title to be determined” [Presentation of the MSCA TaphArt Project]. *University of Witwatersrand*. Johannesburg – South Africa (February 2024).

3.2 Research Skills and techniques:

- Training on sedimentology applied to archaeology. Latin American Geoarchaeological Studies Group (October 23 – November 8, 2023). Instructors: Dr Debora Kligman and Dr Carola Castiñera.
- Training on surface analysis using confocal microscopy. UMR5199 PACEA – University of Bordeaux (December 2023 – March 2024). Instructor: Dr Alain Queffelec.
- Training on physicochemical analyses of ochre pigments. Department of Analytical Chemistry – University of the Basque Country (April – June 2024). Instructor: Prof Maite Maguregui and Dr Francesco Caruso.
- MA in Applied Statistics using R. National University of Distance Education – Spain (December 2024 – September 2025).

3.3 Research management:

- Fellowship or other funding applications planned (indicate name of award if known; include fellowships with entire funding periods, grants written/applied for/received, professional society presentation awards or travel awards, etc.)
- *Wenner-Gren Foundation Workshop Grant*.
Submitted by Neemias Santos Rosa and Ran Barkai on November 20, 2023.
Funding to cover the costs of organizing the workshop “Beyond images: rethinking the presence, absence and meaning of prehistoric and Indigenous rock depictions”. Tel Aviv – Israel (September 2024).
Requested funding: US\$ 20.000
Funding period: September 2024.
Status: under review.

- *GPR “Human Past” call for projects*
To be submitted by Neemias Santos Rosa and Diego Garate on March 29, 2024.
Funding to cover the costs of experiments related to the taphonomy of palaeolithic caves with rock art located in Northern Spain.
Requested funding: EUR 5.000
Funding period: June 2024 – June 2025
Status: To be submitted on March 2024.
- *National Geographic Explorer Grant*
To be submitted by Neemias Santos Rosa and Danae Fiore on April, 2025.
Funding to cover the costs of a study on the pigments and paintings of the Indigenous Peoples of Tierra del Fuego, Patagonia.
Requested funding: US\$ 20.000
Funding Period: September 2025 – September 2026
Status: To be submitted on April 2025.
- *ERC Starting Grant*
To be submitted by Neemias Santos da Rosa on September 2025.
Funding to develop a project on the technology and taphonomy of palaeolithic rock art paintings.
Requested funding: EUR 1.500.000
Funding Period: September 2026 – September 2031
Status: To be submitted on September 2025.

3.4 Communication skills:

- Through the various conferences, workshops, and seminars mentioned in the preceding sections, I will enhance my communication skills, particularly in explaining theoretical and methodological frameworks in English. Additionally, I am having the opportunity to learn how to present my research in Frances.

3.5 Other professional training (course work, teaching activity):

- I am currently co-supervising 3 PhD students:
 1. Alba Salceda – University of Cadiz (Spain)
PhD project title: *La individualidad en el arte rupestre. Análisis de autoría a las manifestaciones gráficas de la Prehistoria Reciente en la provincia de Cádiz: La Cueva del Tajo de las Figuras.*
Expected date of reading: 2026
 2. José Paulo Francisco – University of Barcelona (Spain)
PhD project title: *Os valores do património: uma investigação sobre os sítios pré-históricos de arte rupestre do Vale do Rio Côa e de Siega Verde.*
Expected date of reading: 2025.

3. Jorge del Reguero – University of Barcelona (Spain)

PhD project title: *Historiografía de la arqueología fenicia y púnica en España entre los siglos XIX y XX: configuración, desarrollo y consolidación.*

Expected date of reading: 2025.

- I am also willing to co-supervise a MA student at the University of Bordeaux during the academia year 2024-2025.

3.6 Anticipated networking opportunities

- The MSCA TaphArt project has allowed me to expand my research network and collaborate with researchers from the Department of Analytical Chemistry at the University of the Basque Country (Spain), the Institute of Solar Research at the German Aerospace Center (Germany), the Center for Early Sapiens Behaviour at the University of Bergen (Norway), the International Institute for Prehistoric Research at the University of Cantabria (Spain), and the University of Tel Aviv (Israel). Furthermore, the project has enabled me to strengthen my existing collaborations with researchers from CONICET/University of Buenos Aires (Argentina), the University of Barcelona (Spain), the University of Alicante (Spain) and the University of Cádiz (Spain). Finally, as a result of the project, I was also invited to be an Honorary Research Fellow at the Rock Art Institute at the University of Witwatersrand (South Africa).

3.7 Other activities (community, etc.) with professional relevance:

- Through periodic meetings with the supervisor, I have learned to manage my career and increase my employability. As a result of one of these meetings, I decided to study the MA in Applied Statistics using R.

Date & Signature of fellow:

February 19, 2024.

Date & Signature of supervisor:

February 19, 2024.